

Studies on the Complexes of Alizarin, Quinalizarin and Erichrome Blue Black R with some Rare Earth Salts

S. M. F. Rahman, Naseer Ahmad and Jamil Ahmad

Alizarin, Quinalizarin and Eriochrome Blue Black R form red, light blue, and dark brown coloured complexes with La, Ce, Pr, Nd and Sm. These complexes have been studied spectrophotometrically. The λ_{\max} for alizarin complexes was 535-40 m μ and that for quinalizarin and Erichrome Blue Black R were 575-85 and 530-35 m μ respectively. Job's method of continuous variation as well as molar ratio method showed a combining ratio of 1:2 (metal:dye) for alizarin and quinalizarin complexes and 1:1 for Eriochrome-rare-earth complexes. The log of apparent formation constant for the Eriochrome complexes was 5.2 ± 0.8 .

A-lieva et al¹ reported colour reaction of quinalizarin with Y⁺³, La⁺³, Ce⁺³, Pr⁺³, Nd⁺³ and Gd⁺³ in slightly acidic medium. Korenman² and others, in their investigations on the interaction of rare-earths with alizarin reds and quinalizarin ascertained that all rare earth complexes exhibit maximum absorption in the wave length range of 560-90 m μ and reported a combining ratio of 1 : 1 for various rare-earth elements and quinalizarin. Tataeve and Bagdasaror³ used quinalizarin in the photometric determination of praseodymium. They reported no colour development in the pH range of 1—6.5; complex formation at higher pH values, λ_{\max} at 584 and 658 m μ at pH 7 and 8 — 10 respectively and a molar ratio of 1 : 2 for complex formed between praseodymium and quinalizarin. Lal and Srivastava⁴ have proposed alizarin as a reagent for quantitative analysis of a mixture containing Ce(III) and Ce(IV). The interaction between rare earth salts and Erichrome Blue Black R abbreviated in this paper as EBBR finds little mention in the existing chemical literature.

Our present communication deals with the spectrophotometric studies on the complexes of La, Ce, Pr, Nd and Sm with alizarin, quinalizarin and EBBR.

EXPERIMENTAL

0.24 gm of alizarin, 0.0544 gm of quinalizarin and 0.416 gm of EBBR were dissolved in 1 litre of 98% alcohol separately to obtain $0.2 \times 10^{-3}M$ solution of quinalizarin and $0.1 \times 10^{-2}M$ solution of the other dyes. The pH of alcohol used for alizarin and quinalizarin solutions was adjusted to 6 by adding hydrochloric acid and that for EBBR to 10 by adding requisite amount of caustic soda. LaCl₃, PrCl₃, NdCl₃ and SmCl₃ (A. R. samples, Chemistry

1. M. K. Akhmedli, A. A. Sadykhova, P. B. Granovskaya, I. S. Lozovskaya and S. Alieva, *Azerb. Khim. Zh.* (5), 93-104 (1963) (Russ), *Chem. Abs.*, 1965, **62**, 7106c.
2. I. M. Korenman, V. G. Ganina and N. V. Kurina, *Tr po Khim i Khim Tekhnol.*, 1961, **4**, 761-6; *Chem. Abst.*, 1962, **58**, 9602g.
3. O. A. Tataeve and K. N. Bagdasaror, *Elektrokhim i optich Metody Analiza*, 1963, **8b**, 212-216; *Chem. Abst.* 1964, **61**, 4957a.
4. Sudarshan Lal and S. N. Srivastava, *J. Chem. Education*, 1966, **43**, (8), 424; *Chem. Abst.*, 1966 **65**, 11314c.

Division, AEE Bombay) were dissolved in 98% alcohol of pH 6 or 10 as the case may be to prepare their stock solutions. A known volume of the stock solution was evaporated to dryness, dissolved in distilled water and the rare-earth precipitated as oxalate⁵ and titrated with standard permanganate solution.

Bausch and Lomb spectronic-20 colorimeter was used for spectrophotometric measurements.

The wave length of maximum absorptions by the complexes of alizarin, quinalizarin and EBBR was selected according to the method of Vosburgh and Cooper⁶. $0.166 \times 10^{-3} M$ alizarin, $0.333 \times 10^{-4} M$ or $0.2 \times 10^{-4} M$ solution of quinalizarin or EBBR was mixed with equimolar solution of rare-earth salts in the ratio of 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3, 2 : 1, 3 : 1 and 1 : 0 and their optical density measured at different wave lengths in the visible range. The λ_{max} for alizarin and alizarin-rare earths complexes were at 440 and between 535-40 $m\mu$ respectively. In the case of quinalizarin and quinalizarin rare-earths complexes they were at 500 and between 575-85 $m\mu$ respectively. The same for EBBR and EBBR-rare earths complexes was between 535-40 $m\mu$.

Fig 1(a) Job's Method

FIG. 1a

5. James Frederick Spencer, "The Metals of the Rare Earths", Longmans Green, London, 1919, pp. 135-6

6. W. C. Vosburgh and G. R. Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, (1941), **63**, 437,

FIG. 1b

FIG. 1c

Lambert's and Beer's Law was found to hold good in the approximate concentration range of 0.166×10^{-5} — $1.6 \times 10^{-4} M$, 0.166×10^{-5} — $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, and 0.166×10^{-5} — $0.9 \times 10^{-4} M$, for the rare-earth alizarin mixtures in the ratio of 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 4 respectively. The range for rare earth quinalizarin mixtures in the above ratio was 1.666×10^{-6} — 6.66

$\times 10^{-5}M$, 1.666×10^{-5} — $5.0 \times 10^{-5}M$ and 1.66×10^{-6} — $4.0 \times 10^{-5}M$ respectively. The same for rare-earth EBBR mixtures in the ratio of 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 was 0.125×10^{-5} — $6 \times 10^{-5}M$, 0.125×10^{-5} — $2.7 \times 10^{-5}M$ and 0.125×10^{-5} — $2.0 \times 10^{-5}M$ respectively.

Job's method of continuous variation⁷ was performed at the corresponding wave length maxima with equimolar concentrations of the rare earth salts and dyes. In the case of alizarin complexes the concentration of the solutions used were $0.25 \times 10^{-3}M$, $0.20 \times 10^{-3}M$ and $0.10 \times 10^{-3}M$. The same for quinalizarin complexes were $0.2 \times 10^{-3}M$, $0.125 \times 10^{-3}M$ and $0.10 \times 10^{-3}M$. Job's method for EBBR rare earths complexes were performed at $0.8 \times 10^{-4}M$, $0.666 \times 10^{-4}M$ and $0.50 \times 10^{-4}M$ concentrations. The difference in the optical densities of the mixture of the dye and the rare-earths salts and the corresponding concentration of the dye was plotted against the composition of the mixture. The rare-earth salts solutions at such a high dilution possess no appreciable absorption (fig. 1a, 1b and 1c).

Molar⁸ ratio method was employed to confirm the results obtained from Job's method. 2 ml solution of the rare-earth salt was taken in each of the 12 test tubes and varying volumes of the equimolar concentrations of the dye were added. The total volume was made to 12 ml by adding requisite volume of alcohol. The difference in the optical density was plotted against the volume of the dye.

In another set of experiments the volume of the dye was kept constant at 4 ml and varying volumes of the rare-earth salts solutions were added and the volume was made up

FIG. 2a

7. P. Job, *Compt. rend.*, 1925, **180**, 928.8. J. H. Yoc and A. L. Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.* 1944, **16**, 111.

to 12 ml by addition of alcohol. In another test tube 4 ml of the dye was taken and alcohol was added to make the volume 12 ml. The difference in the optical densities of the mixture of the rare-earth-dye and that of the dye were plotted against the volume of the rare-earth. Such experiments were performed for the complexes of alizarin and quinalizarin with La, Ce, Pr, Nd and Sm.

FIG. 2b

In the case of EBBR complexes for molar ratio method similar experiments were completed but the constant volumes of the rare-earths salts or the dye were 3 ml only.

The concentrations used in the molar ratio method were $0.25 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $0.2 \times 10^{-3} M$ for alizarin complexes, $0.2 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $0.125 \times 10^{-3} M$ in the case of quinalizarin complexes and 0.5×10^{-4} and $0.666 \times 10^{-4} M$ for that of EBBR complexes.

FIG. 2c

The apparent formation constants of the complexes of alizarin and quinalizarin were calculated by the method of Banerji and Dey⁹ from Job's curves which were drawn with

the optical density of the mixture as ordinate. The apparent formation constant of EBBR complexes were calculated from the Job's curves using the formula

$$K = \frac{x}{(a_1 - x)(b_1 - x)} = \frac{x}{(a_2 - x)(b_2 - x)}$$

where a_1 , a_2 , b_1 and b_2 were concentrations of the metal salts and EBBR at two points on two curves such that the optical density on them was the same.

DISCUSSION

Job's method yielded the combining ratio of 1 : 2 (metal-dye) for La, Ce, Pr, Nd and Sm complexes of alizarin and quinalizarin. The same ratio was confirmed by the two sets of molar ratio method. EBBR complexes with these metal salts gave a ratio of 1 : 1 (metal : EBBR). This ratio was verified by molar ratio methods.

The log of apparent formation constant for the complexes of EBBR with La, Ce, Pr, Nd and Sm was 5.2 ± 0.8 . The various values of apparent formation constants calculated for the complexes of alizarin and quinalizarin differed markedly and no definite value could be determined for each complex.

Author's thanks are due to Prof. A. R. Kidwai for providing facilities to carry out these investigations.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
ALIGARH MUSLIM UNIVERSITY,
ALIGARH,

Received, September 9, 1967.